

A DAY WITH THE EDCH

Let's take a look at what a typical day with the EDCH might look like!

Step 1. Connect

JOIN THE EUROPEAN DIAMOND OA COMMUNITY

By joining, you open the door to a world of collaboration, support, and valuable resources that will guide you through the entire European Diamond OA landscape.

FOR YOU

You are involved in the European Diamond OA publishing landscape?
You are a member of an organisation listed in the EDCH Registry?
Well, it's time to engage.

Forum.

A dynamic virtual space designed to foster collaboration, dialogue, and knowledge sharing.

WHY

- Share your experiences and good practices with peers.
- Ask your questions, get help, solve your issues.
- Tap into expertise available outside your community.
- Co-create a virtual space to interact and contribute to a dynamic community of practice.

HOW

- Visit the [EDCH Forum](#).
- Create a personal account.
- Join discussions, ask questions, and collaborate with others.

Step 2. Grow

STRENGTHEN YOUR PRACTICES

SELF-ASSESS: KNOW WHERE YOU STAND

Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) and its self-assessment tools.

Evaluate your current practices and identify areas for improvement to meet high standards in transparency, sustainability, and operational quality.

WHY

- Benchmark your publishing operations.
- Align with DOAS.
- Enhance credibility and transparency.
- Receive guidance on improving operational standards.

HOW

- Discover and apply [DOAS](#) best practices.
- Complete the [Self-Assessment](#) to evaluate your compliance.

IMPROVE: PRACTICAL TOOLS AND TRAINING

Resources & Guidelines.

Access practical toolkits, policy recommendations, and best-practice guides to improve your publishing workflows and ensure DOAS compliance.

WHY

- Get actionable insights on how to improve your publishing practices.
- Ensure your journal aligns with international best practices.
- Access high-level introductions to Diamond OA principles.

HOW

- Simply go to the [Resources & Guidelines](#) website and start discovering all our resources!

Training Platform.

Skill-building modules that cover everything from technical publishing workflows to strategies for sustainable, high-quality publishing practices.

WHY

- Build expertise in Diamond OA publishing operations.
- Identify a training that matches your needs and interests.
- Stay up-to-date with the latest developments, tools, and compliance standards.

HOW

- Visit the [Training Platform](#).
- Create a personal account.
- Start exploring the courses!

Publishing Tools.

Streamline your publishing workflows with our set of open, flexible, and interoperable software solutions designed to improve your editorial and technical workflows.

WHY

- Ensure seamless interoperability between different software and platforms.
- Reduce technical barriers and focus on content and community.
- Strengthen the sustainability of your publishing operations.

HOW

- Visit the [Publishing Tools](#) website.
- Explore the available software solutions.
- Implement the tools that best fit your workflow.

COMING SOON

Step 3. Shine

INCREASE YOUR VISIBILITY

FOR YOUR ORGANISATION

You are an European Diamond OA publisher?

An European Diamond OA service provider?

An European Diamond OA tools & technology provider?

Well, it's time to register.

Registry.

Present and promote your organisation profile, highlight its expertise, services, and operational capacities in Diamond OA publishing.

WHY

- Join a growing community of publishers, service providers, and tools and technology providers.
- Become visible within the European Diamond OA landscape.
- Get recognition for your role in strengthening Diamond OA publishing.
- Start building your collaboration network and find collaborators and partners.

HOW

- Visit the [Registry](#).
- Click "Register" and create your personal account.
- Complete your organisation's profile.
- Submit – our team will review and verify your entry.

FOR YOUR JOURNAL

You are an European Diamond OA journal?

You comply with the six operational criteria for Diamond OA?

Well, it's also time to register.

The Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH).

A central registry for Diamond OA journals in Europe, your gateway to greater visibility, trust, and impact.

WHY

- Increase the discoverability of your journals by researchers, institutions, and funders across Europe and beyond.
- Gain trust and recognition as you demonstrate commitment to Diamond OA.
- Participate in building a fairer and more sustainable scholarly publishing system.

COMING SOON

